

AgroPV Potential, Opportunities and Barriers in Turkey: A Preliminary Evaluation From Social Sciences Perspective (in Turkish)

Theme: Energy, European Research Area and SSH Aspects

Seven Ađır

Dep. of Economics / Middle East Technical University

Moderator: Esin Yazıcı

Live Seminar Time and Date: 12:00-13:00 (Turkish time / GMT + 3)

Friday, June 24, 2022

Register at: <https://forms.gle/i6RxqU6YxiYLWU3s6>

Moderation: PhDc. Esin Yazıcı

Registration for live seminar closes at 20:00, Thursday, 23 June 2022: To receive the link to the live seminar you must register by 20:00, Thursday 23 June 2022.

Abstract: In AgroPV (agrophotovoltaic) applications, in which renewable energy production and agricultural production are combined through photovoltaic panels on agricultural land, has come to the fore as an innovative application that alleviates or eliminates competition on land use, especially with the widespread use of renewable energy production in developed countries. In Turkey, although there is not yet a fully-fledged legislation in this area, both the increasing risks in terms of agricultural yields and income due climate change and the rising financial difficulties due to increased input (especially energy) costs indicate that AgroPV may have a strong potential not only in terms of the widespread use of renewable energy but also in terms of sustainability of agricultural production. Yet, there are few studies exploring factors that enable or hinder farmers' acceptance and adoption of AgroPV. In this study, we will present how social sciences (in particular scholarship on the behavioral aspects of agricultural production) can contribute to our understanding of farmers' adoption of new technologies in general and AgroPV in particular. The theoretical discussion will be complemented by a preliminary analysis of in-depth interviews that were conducted with "pioneer/expert" farmers in Turkey.

Speaker:

Assoc. Prof. Dr. Seven Ađır holds a Ph.D. from Princeton University, completed her post-doctoral research at Yale University and joined faculty at Middle East Technical University, Economics Department in 2012. She has done extensive research on the institutional-historical aspects of business organizations as part of a Marie Curie Career integration grant. She is currently working on several projects concerning sustainable agriculture and food security exploring 'the impact of urban sprawl on peri-urban agriculture in Ankara,' 'the factors underlying adoption of sustainable agriculture by Turkish farmers' and 'social and economic analysis of AgroPV.' of Turkish research universities.

About SolarTwins- TEKPOL Seminars: The path to a prosperous, sustainable, and secure Turkey includes a Clean Energy Transition (CET) and Green Economy Transition (GET). Many of the largest challenges to be solved to realize these transitions lie at the intersection of technology and policy. Some of these challenges are unique to a specific technology, while others are cross-cutting challenges that underpin the competitiveness of Turkey's Research and Innovation (R&I) ecosystem. This SolarTwins-TEKPOL Pizza Seminar series aims to provide a scientific forum to increase awareness of these challenges and contribute to the co-creation of solutions to overcome these challenges. This series is designed as a part of SolarTwins Project Joint Research Line 9: Social Aspects of Sustainable Energy Transitions

About SolarTwins: SolarTwins is a European Union Horizon 2020 (H2020) project coordinated by ODTÜ-GÜNAM through METU with CIEMAT-PSA (Spain) and DLR (Germany) as partners. The objectives of the SolarTwins project are to

1. Step-up the scientific excellence of the Concentrating Solar Thermal (CST) Research Division ODAK of ODTÜ-GÜNAM through capacity building activities in collaboration with the globally leading CST institutions CIEMAT-PSA and DLR.
2. Strengthen METU, ODTÜ-GÜNAM, and Turkey's horizontal Research and Innovation (R&I) Capacities.

About METU TEKPOL: Science and Technology Policy Studies (STPS) program was founded in 1997 at the Middle East Technical University with the explicit objective to supply science and technology policy related human capital for the government bodies, agencies and other related organizations and to conduct research in science, technology and innovation policy issues. It has organic relations with the Research Center for Science and Technology Policies. Education and research elements integrate under METU-TEKPOL. TEKPOL is the only academic unit in Turkey that concurrently coordinates education and research activities. It operates M.Sc. and Ph.D. programs in science technology policy studies at the Graduate School of Social Sciences. TEKPOL also conducts interdisciplinary research on science and technology policy issues with the aim of addressing societal challenges.

PROGRAMME:

Date	Speaker, Institution	Seminar Title
15 April 2022	Arda MEVLÜTOĞLU, Kubilay YILDIRIM and Semih AKÇOMAK	TOGG and Beyond (in Turkish) – Panel
22 April 2022	Onur Çağdaş ARTANTAŞ	Promotion of Green Electricity: Legal and Political Perspectives (in Turkish)
29 April 2022	Serdar TÜRKELİ	Technological change and non-intervention, novel indicators and non-measurement (in Turkish)
13 May 2022	Barbel EPP	Cost Trends for Commercial and Industrial Solar Heat
20 May 2022	Pınar DERİN GÜRE	Gender and social sciences involvement in technology development projects in energy (in Turkish)
27 May 2022	Şuhsnaz YILMAZ ÖZBAĞCI	Sustainable Energy and Climate Policies in the Light of Changing Global and Regional Dynamics (in Turkish)
3 June 2022	Derek BAKER	ODAK _{TR} : Concentrating Solar Thermal (CST) as a key enabling technology for Turkey's Clean Energy Transition.
10 June 2022	Christian OLTRA	Introducing SSH aspects of Energy Transitions
17 June 2022	S. Banu AKKAŞ, Zelal ÖZDEMİR	METU in New European Research Area (in Turkish)
24 June 2022	Seven AĞIR	AgroPV Potential, Opportunities and Barriers in Turkey: A Preliminary Evaluation From Social Sciences Perspective

Contact: Yelda ERDEN TOPAL
yeldae@metu.edu.tr

ERKAN ERDİL
erdil@metu.edu.tr

Derek K. BAKER
dbaker@metu.edu.tr

SolarTwins has received funding from the European Union Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement No 856619.